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Impact of E-Learning Machine Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Impact of E-Learning Machine Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. A pre-test post-test quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. Simple Random Sampling technique was used to select two co-educational schools from the target population. The sample of the study consisted of 122 students, in which 60 are male while 62 are female Senior Secondary class two students during 2024/2025 academic session in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State. The instrument used for data collection was E-Learning Machine Model Test (EMMT). The EMMT had a reliability index of 0.88 using Test-retest reliability test which implies that the instrument is significant. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while the null-hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Independent Sample t-test statistics. The results of the study revealed that students taught mathematics using E-Learning machine model performed significantly better than those taught the same contents using the conventional method. The study also revealed that both male and female students in the experimental group performed significantly better. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that teachers should be trained on how to use e-learning machine model effectively in their teaching practices through workshops and seminars.

Keywords: E-learning machine model, achievement, mathematics concepts.

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Introduction

Mathematics provides a fundamental framework for comprehending the intricacies of the physical world, enabling the interpretation of spatial and temporal relationships. Its significance extends to underpinning scientific and technological advancements, which in turn drive socio-economic development. Consequently, mathematics education is mandatory in Nigerian primary and secondary schools. Furthermore, proficiency in mathematics is a prerequisite for admission into esteemed university programs, including engineering, medicine, and accounting, highlighting its crucial role in academic and professional pursuits. Mathematics is a vital subject that extends beyond academic qualifications, as it equips students with essential skills for future success, regardless of their chosen career path (Davies & Hersh, 2012). This notion is reinforced by Mefor (2014), who succinctly emphasizes that mathematics relates to everything across the universe, from the smallest scales to the vast expanse of the universe.

Despite its pivotal role in societal development, mathematics is often a source of anxiety, failure, and disdain among students (Areelu, 2014). The subject has long been perceived as the most challenging component of the school curriculum, fostering a pervasive negative attitude among learners that transcends generations. This entrenched mindset, which extends to adults who have previously struggled with mathematics, can lead to a devaluation of the subject's importance, ultimately influencing the effectiveness of educators' teaching efforts (Ajani & Konku, 2012).

Mathematics education is a multidisciplinary field that focuses on the development and implementation of effective methods, tools, and approaches to teach and learn mathematics. At the higher education level, mathematics education aims to equip students with advanced mathematical skills, quantitative reasoning, and symbolic manipulation through various programs, including general education, services, majors, and graduate studies. According to Odili (2012), mathematicians can be broadly classified into two categories: mathematics educators and professional mathematicians. Mathematics educators specialize in curriculum design, instructional development, and pedagogical innovation, whereas professional mathematicians focus on advancing mathematical knowledge and applications.

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Mathematics education fundamentally aims to cultivate innovative instructors who can effectively communicate mathematical concepts to learners across various levels. Mathematics educators perceive mathematics as a dynamic field of practice, rather than merely a static body of knowledge or academic discipline. As Lester (2002) notes, this perspective emphasizes the importance of understanding how mathematics is learned, interpreted, and applied, as well as how individuals conceptualize and utilize mathematics in their daily lives. Furthermore, educators seek to bridge the gap between mathematical concepts taught in schools and their real-world applications. The rapid evolution of technology has significantly impacted the educational landscape, enabling unprecedented opportunities for learning and interaction, even in remote and underserved regions.

The widespread adoption of Information Communication Technology (ICT) necessitates the evolution of education through e-learning platforms. As underscored by Adeyinka and Olusola (2009), the integration of ICT into educational settings enhances the learning experience, organisational structure, and administrative efficiency of institutions. Furthermore, the internet has emerged as a transformative force, significantly contributing to the advancement of educational development and bridging the knowledge gap. The integration of technology in education has transformed the way students learn and teachers teach. E-learning leverages information and communication technology (ICT) to facilitate a seamless exchange of knowledge between educators and learners across all educational levels, thereby marking a significant milestone in the advancement of education.

E-learning machine models are computational models that utilise machine learning algorithms to analyse learner's behaviour, preferences, and performance, and adapt the learning content, pace and style to meet individual learner needs (Kotsiantis, 2012). Research by Stephen (2023) has demonstrated that the integration of e-learning machine models in education improved outcomes, enhanced student engagement, and increased support for teachers. E-learning machine models can significantly improve teaching and learning outcomes in mathematics education for sustainable development in secondary schools in several ways which include, Adaptive Learning, Learning Pathways, Interactive Simulations, Real-world applications and Learning analytics among others (Koedinger et al., 2013).

Adaptive Learning: E-learning machine models can adjust the difficulty level of mathematical problems and provide real-time feedback, catering to individual

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students' needs and abilities (Koedinger et al., 2013). Furthermore, in terms of learning pathways, Machine learning algorithms can create personalized learning pathways for students, recommending relevant mathematical concepts and resources based on their learning history and performance (Romero & Ventura, 2010). Interactive simulations: E-learning machine models can provide interactive simulations and games that make mathematical concepts more engaging and accessible, promoting active learning and exploration (Hansen et al., 2016). Real-world applications, Machine learning models can help students connect mathematical concepts to real-world sustainable development challenges, making learning more relevant and meaningful (Ernest, 2012). Efficient assessment and feedback to automated grading, E-learning machine models can automate the grading process, freeing up instructors' time to focus on providing feedback and support (Baker et al., 2016). Real-time feedback, Machine learning algorithms can provide immediate feedback to students on their performance, helping them identify areas of improvement and track their progress (Koedinger et al., 2013).

Learning analytics: E-learning machine models can provide instructors with valuable insights into student learning behavior, helping them identify knowledge gaps and adjust their instruction accordingly (Siemens, 2013). Moreso in the area of predictive modelling, machine learning algorithms can predict student performance and enabling instructors to provide targeted support and interventions (Romero & Ventura, 2010). E-learning machine models have emerged as a promising tool for improving teaching and learning outcomes in mathematics. This study therefore, investigates the impact of e-learning machine model on teaching and learning in mathematics education for sustainable development in senior secondary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the crucial role of mathematics education in sustainable development, students continue to show weakness in attempting Mathematics examination questions. WAEC Chief Examiner's report 20223 pointed out eleven (11) areas of students' weaknesses against three (3) areas of strength in answering mathematics examination questions which is worrisome. The traditional teaching methods, which emphasize lecturing and rote memorization, have been criticized for failing to promote deep understanding, critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Nwafor, 2017). Furthermore, the absence of adequate instructional materials, including e-learning resources, has hindered the effective teaching and learning of mathematics. Researchers have explored various factors contributing to the poor

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performance in mathematics, Impact of E-Learning Machine Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria remain understudied, highlighting the need for an investigation into the potential benefits of integrating e-learning machine model into mathematics education in secondary schools. The use of e-learning machine model has the potential to address these challenges and improve teaching and learning outcomes in Mathematics (Ahn & Edwin, 2018). Based on these factors, the researcher wishes to investigate Impact of E-Learning Machine Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the Study

The study has the following objectives:

1. To determine the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using E-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State
2. To determine the mean achievement scores of Male and Female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State

Research questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State

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Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental control group design employing pre-test and post-test. Quasi-experimental design was adopted because the researcher has no total control over the study subjects. The study involved two groups; one experimental group and one control group which were drawn from the population of senior secondary class two (SSII) in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State. The experimental group was taught mathematics using E-learning Machine Model while the control group was taught mathematics using the conventional method. The population of the study consisted of 7,550 students from all the senior secondary schools in Zaria Metropolis. Then a sample of 122 was randomly selected from two senior secondary schools, in which 60 are male and 62 are female students. The instrument used for the study was E-Learning Machine Model Test (EMMT). The face and content validity of the instrument was vetted by the experts in Mathematics department, experts in the department of Test and Measurement evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined by using Test-retest reliability test which was analysed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation analysis that yielded the reliability coefficient of 0.88. The data collected were subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered with the use of mean and standard deviation while the research hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Result

The results of the study were obtained from the research questions answered and hypotheses formulated for the study;

Research question one

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Achievement Scores in Mathematics of both the Experimental Group and Control Group after the Treatment.

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	64	50.18	9.07	

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Control	58	39.53	12.54	10.65
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The result in Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of the students' achievement scores in mathematics between the experimental group and the control group. The results revealed that the experimental group had the mean score of (50.18) while the control group had the mean score of (39.53). The mean difference between the experimental and control group was 10.65. This implies that the experimental group that was taught mathematics with e-Learning machine model performed significantly better than the control group that was mathematics using lecture method.

Null Hypothesis One:

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State. This was analysed using Independent Sample t-test, the summary of the result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Independent sample t-test analysis on the students' post-test in the Experimental and Control group after treatment

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Experimental	64	50.18	9.07	120	20.05	0.001	*
Control	58	39.53	12.54				

* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

The independent sample t-test result in Table 2, shows that the difference in the test scores between the experimental group (N=64, M=50.18, SD=9.07) and control group (N=58, M=39.53, SD=12.54) were statistically significant. t-value = 20.05 and the p-value of 0.001 was less than $\alpha \leq 0.05$. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was rejected, which shows that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method. Since the mean score of the experimental group is higher than the control group it therefore implies that the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics with e-learning machine model enhances the academic achievement of secondary school students in mathematics than the conventional method.

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Research question two

What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State? Summary of the mean and standard deviation is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Achievement Scores in Mathematics for both Male and Female students in the Experimental Group

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Male	33	43.05	20.20	1.04
Female	31	42.01	20.10	

The result in Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of both male and female students' achievement scores in mathematics within the experimental group. The results revealed that the male students had the mean score of (43.05) while the female students had the mean score of (42.01). The mean difference between the male and the female students in the experimental group was 1.04. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model in the experimental group.

Null Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State. This was analysed using Independent Sample t-test, the summary of the result is presented in Table 4:

Table 4: Independent sample t-test analysis on male and female students' achievement in mathematics within the Experimental group

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Male	33	43.05	20.20	62	0.19	0.79	**
Female	31	42.01	20.10				

** Not significant $p > 0.05$

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The result in Table 4, showed an independent sample t-test of the difference in the test scores between the male students (N=33, M=43.05, SD=20.20) and the female students (N=31, M=42.01, SD=20.10) were statistically not significant. t-value = 0.19 and the p-value of 0.79 was greater than $\alpha \leq 0.05$. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was retained, this means that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State. Thus, e-learning machine model enhances the academic performance of both male and female students in mathematics.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that the experimental group who were taught mathematics using e-learning machine model performed significantly better than those taught mathematics using the conventional method. The difference was in favour of the experimental group; this could be due to the fact that e-learning machine model allows active participation of students than the conventional method which is teacher centre method. Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of e-learning machine models in improving student learning outcomes in mathematics. For instance, a study by Koedinger et al. (2013) found that students who used an intelligent tutoring system (ITS) for mathematics performed better than those who received traditional instruction. Similarly, a study by Ritter et al. (2017) found that students who used a computer-based mathematics tutor outperformed those who received traditional instruction.

Furthermore, the result of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of both male and female students in mathematics when taught with e-learning machine model. This shows that e-learning machine model is gender friendly and improves the performance of both male and female students in mathematics. This is in accordance with the findings of Wang et al. (2016) who found that girls who used a computer-based mathematics program performed as well as boys, suggesting that technology-based instruction can help reduce the gender gap in mathematics achievement. More so, the use of e-learning machine models has been shown to promote sustainable development in education. A study by UNESCO (2017) highlighted the potential of technology-based instruction to promote sustainable development in education. Overall, the findings of this study contribute to the growing

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body of research that supports the use of e-learning machine models to improve teaching and learning in mathematics education.

Conclusion

This study concludes that e-learning machine models have a positive impact on students' achievement in mathematics concepts among senior secondary school students in Zaria. The use of e-learning machine models enhances students' achievement in mathematics, promotes student-centered learning methods, and improves overall teaching and learning outcomes. Both male and female students performed relatively equally when taught using e-learning machine models. Therefore, teachers should be encouraged to integrate e-learning machine models into their teaching practices for both boys and girls, while conventional learning methods should be supplemented to enhance learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Schools should invest in e-learning technologies to enhance the teaching and learning of mathematics, ensuring accessibility for both teachers and students.
2. Teachers should receive continuous professional development through workshops and seminars on the effective integration of e-learning tools into their instructional practices.
3. Policymakers should formulate and implement strategic policies that support the adoption and sustainability of e-learning technologies in secondary schools

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References

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Adeyinka, T. & Olusola, A. (2009). Nigeria ICT & curriculum development: The challenges for education for sustainable development. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*. 2(3)45.

Ahn, J.Y. & Edwin, A. (2018). An e-learning model for teaching mathematics on an open-source learning platform. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning. IRRODL*. 19(5), 23-28.

Ajani, T. O. & Konku, A. A. (2012). Effect of computer assisted instruction (CAI) on the teaching and learning of mathematics in senior secondary school in Ogun State. *COEASU Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*. 3(1), 68-75.

Areelu, F. (2014). *Effects of tiered lesson and group personalization instructional on senior secondary school students' interest and achievement in mathematics in Lagos state*. Unpublished PhD thesis, university of Ibadan, Ibadan.

Baker, R. S. J. d., Corbett, A. T., & Koedinger, K. R. (2016). The role of intelligent tutoring systems in education. In R. K. Sawyer (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of the Learning Sciences*. 561- 584. Cambridge University Press.

Davies, P.J. & Hersh, R. (2012). *The mathematical experience*. Boston: Mifflin Company.

Ernest, P. (2012). The relationship between mathematics and sustainability. *Journal for the Learning of Mathematics*. 32(2), 2-7.

Hansen, J. J., Larson, L. R., & Snow, E. L. (2016). Exploring the potential of simulations in mathematics education. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*. 19 (2-3), 143-165.

Koedinger, K. R., Corbett, A. T., & Perfetti, C. (2013). The Knowledge-Learning-Instruction (KLI) framework: Toward a unified science of learning. In R. K. Sawyer (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of the Learning Sciences*. 119-144. Cambridge University Press.

Kotsiantis, S. B. (2012). Use of machine learning algorithms for educational purposes: A review. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*. 4(1), 1-18.

Lester, F. K. (2002). Implications of research on mathematics education for practice. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*. 33(5), 343-355.

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- Mefor, C. (2014). Nigeria: Identifying problems of poor performance in mathematics and way-out. <http://allafrica.com/stories/201101200591.html>
- Nwafor, M.C. (2017). *Effect Conceptual and Procedural Teaching Strategies on Performance in Trigonometry among Secondary School Students in Zaria Education Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis, Faculty of Education Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Odili, G. O. (2012). Towards a new paradigm of teaching mathematics in Nigerian universities: The role of mathematics educators. *Journal of Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria (STAN)*. 47(1), 130-135.
- Ritter, S., Anderson, J. R., Koedinger, K. R., & Corbett, A. (2017). Cognitive Tutor: Applied research in mathematics education. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*. 14(2), 249-255.
- Siemens, G. (2013). Learning analytics: The emergence of a discipline. *Journal of American Behavioral Scientist*. 57(10), 1380-1400.
- Romero, C., & Ventura, S. (2010). Educational data mining: A review of the state-of-the-art. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C. Applications and Reviews*. 40(6), 601- 618.
- UNESCO (2017). Education for Sustainable development goals: Learning objectives. UNESCO.
- Wang, A. Y., & Lee, J. (2016). Gender differences in mathematics achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*. 18(1), 1-13.
- West African Examination Council (WAEC), Chief Examiner's Report (2023).